
Aliphatic esters and fatty acids from the fruits of *Lycium chinense miller*

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Abstract The fruits of *Lycium chinense* Miller (Solanaceae) possess emmenagogue, diuretic, antipyretic and hepatoprotective properties and are used to stimulate the immune system, to increase hormonal growth, to improve blood circulation and eye sight and to cure morning sickness. Phytochemical investigation of a chloroform extract of the fruits gave two new aliphatic esters, characterized as *n*-butanyl *n*-octadec-9,12-dienoate (*n*-butanyl linoleate, **1**) and *n*-tridecanyl *n*-octadec-9,12-dienoate (*n*-tridecanyl linoleate, **2**) and two new fatty acids identified as *cis,cis,cis*-*n*-octacos-5,8,11-trienoic acid (**4**) and *cis*-*n*-octacos-11-enoic acid (**5**) and along with a known saturated fatty acid, arachidic acid (**3**). The structures of these phytoconstituents have been elucidated on the basis of spectral analysis and chemical reactions.

Keywords *Lycium chinense*, fruits, aliphatic esters, fatty acids, structure elucidation.

Introduction

Lycium chinense Miller (Solanaceae), known as Goji berry or Gou-qu-zi, is a cold-hard, perennial shrub. Its origin is believed to be in the region of south-eastern Europe and south-western Asia, but now it is cultivated throughout the world. Today China is the largest producer of this fruit. The dried form of this fruit is emmenagogue, diuretic, antipyretic and hepatoprotective and marketed in Ayurvedic and herbal health shops as the Tibetan or Himalayan Goji berry. The red-orange ellipsoid fruits stimulate the immune system due to high vitamin C contents, increase human growth hormone and sperm production and improve blood circulation and eye sight. The berries are taken by pregnant females to prevent morning sickness and to alleviate hepatitis and insomnia, to improve memory, to provide longevity and as a tonic in traditional oriental medicine. The fruits exhibited hypotensive, hypoglycaemic and antipyretic activities [1, 2]. They have properties like nourishing the blood, enriching the yin, tonifying the kidney and the liver, and moistening the lungs [2, 3]. They are useful for reducing the risk of certain diseases such as arteriosclerosis, essential arterial hypertension, diabetes and night blindness [4-9]. The dried ripe fruits are an ingredient of herbal drugs and functional foods [10]. Goji berry contained sterols, polysaccharides, zeaxanthin and antioxidants like as lutein, β -carotene, vitamin C and lycopene. Potentially hepatoprotective glycolipid constituents and determination of betain in *L. chinense* fruits have been reported [11, 12]. Di- and tetraterpene glycosides and polyglycosides of fatty acids are published in recent reports from *L. chinense* fruits [13-16]. This paper describes isolation and characterization of aliphatic constituents from the berries of *L. chinense* available locally.

Materials and Methods

General

Melting points were determined on a Perfit apparatus without correction. The IR spectra were measured in KBr pellet on a Bio-Red FT-IR spectrometer. Ultraviolet (UV) spectra were obtained in methanol with a Lambda Bio 20 spectrometer. The ^1H (400 MHz), ^{13}C (100 MHz), COSY and HMBC NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectropin spectrometer. CDCl_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, Bangalore, India) was used as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. ESI MS analyses were performed on a Waters Q-TOF Premier (Micromass MS Technologies, Manchester, UK) Mass Spectrometer. Column chromatography separations were carried out on silica gel (Merck, 60–120 mesh, Mumbai, India). Precoated silica gel plates (Merck, Silica gel 60 F_{254}) were used for analytical thin layer chromatography and visualized by exposure to iodine vapours and UV radiations.

Plant material

The fruits of *L. chinense* were procured from a local market of Delhi and identified by Dr. H.B. Singh, Scientist F and Head, Raw Materials Herbarium and Museum, National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR), New Delhi. A voucher specimen of drug was deposited in the herbarium of Phytochemistry Research Laboratory, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi.

Extraction and isolation

The fruits of *L. chinense* (500 g) were coarsely powdered and extracted exhaustively with chloroform using a Soxhlet apparatus for 18 h. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to get dark brown mass (103 g). The residue (100 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of methanol and adsorbed on silica gel column grade (60–120 mesh) to obtain a slurry. The slurry was dried in air and chromatographed over silica gel column loaded in chloroform. The column was eluted with petroleum ether, petroleum ether-chloroform (9:1, 3:1, 1:1, v/v) mixtures and chloroform to obtain compounds **1 - 5**.

n-Butanyl linoleate (1)

Elution of the column with petroleum ether gave pale yellow gummy mass of **1**, IR ν_{max} (KBr): 2928, 2842, 1725, 1635, 1465, 1380, 1262, 1171, 722 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 5.33 (1H, m, H-9), 5.29 (1H, m, H-10), 5.25 (1H, m, H-12), 5.22 (1H, m, H-13), 4.13 (2H, t, $J=6.9$ Hz, H_2-1'), 2.75 (2H, m, H_2-11), 2.33 (2H, t, $J=7.2$ Hz, H_2-2), 2.02 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.98 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.62 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.29 (8H, brs, $4 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.25 (10H, brs, $5 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.89 (3H, t, $J=6.5$ Hz, Me-18), 0.85 (3H, t, $J=6.6$ Hz, Me-4'); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 173.69 (C-1), 131.16 (C-9), 130.48 (C-10), 129.80 (C-12), 127.83 (C-13), 61.05 (C-1'), 34.31 (CH_2), 31.89 (CH_2), 29.79-29.11 ($9 \times \text{CH}_2$), 27.21 (CH_2), 24.93 (CH_2), 22.69 (CH_2), 14.18 (Me-18), 14.09 (Me-4'); +ve ion FAB MS m/z (*rel. int.*): 337 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ ($\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{43}\text{O}_2$) (9.8), 279 (13.1), 263 (15.3).

n-Tridecanyl linoleate (2)

Elution of the column with petroleum ether-chloroform (9:1) yielded a pale yellow gummy mass of **2**, IR ν_{max} (KBr): 2928, 2845, 1723, 1640, 1465, 1363, 1262, 1170, 723 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 5.35 (1H, m, H-9), 5.32 (1H, m, H-10), 5.29 (1H, m, H-12), 5.27 (1H, m, H-13), 4.15 (2H, t, $J=7.2$ Hz, H_2-1'), 2.75 (2H, m, H_2-11), 2.35 (2H, t, $J=7.3$ Hz, H_2-2), 2.01 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.98 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.62 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.56 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.28 (4H, brs, $4 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.25 (26H, brs, $13 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.86 (3H, t, $J=6.6$ Hz, Me-18), 0.83 (3H, t, $J=6.5$ Hz, Me-13'); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 173.67 (C-1), 130.32 (C-9), 127.81 (C-10), 129.52 (C-12), 127.91 (C-13), 60.83 (C-1'), 34.11 (CH_2), 33.93 (CH_2), 31.85 (CH_2), 29.71-29.03 ($18 \times \text{CH}_2$), 28.93 (CH_2), 27.15 (CH_2), 22.68 (CH_2), 14.15 (Me-18), 14.09 (Me-13'); +ve ion FAB MS m/z (*rel. int.*): 463 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ ($\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{59}\text{O}_2$) (23.8), 279 (37.9), 263 (32.1).

Arachidic acid (3)

Elution of the column with petroleum ether-chloroform (3:1) afforded colourless crystals of **3**, IR ν_{max} (KBr): 3090, 2926, 2838, 1702, 1465, 1298, 725 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 2.33 (2H, t, $J=7.5$ Hz, H_2-2), 1.66 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.29 (10H, brs, $5 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.25 (20H, brs, $10 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.88 (3H, t, $J=6.5$ Hz, Me-20); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): δ 179.73 (C-1), 33.98 (CH_2), 31.89 (CH_2), 29.68 ($9 \times \text{CH}_2$), 29.58 (CH_2), 29.44 (CH_2), 29.35 (CH_2), 29.28 (CH_2), 29.06 (CH_2),

24.66 (CH₂), 22.68 (CH₂), 14.16 (Me-20); +ve ion FAB MS *m/z* (*rel. int.*): 313 [M+H]⁺ (C₂₀H₄₁O₂) (12.4), 295 (18.8).

***n*-Octacos-5,8,11-trienoic acid (4)**

Elution of the column with petroleum ether-chloroform (1:1) furnished yellow semisolid mass of **4**, IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 3210, 2917, 2850, 1709, 1640, 1463, 1410, 1295, 1187, 942, 722 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 5.40 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =7.1 Hz, H-5), 5.36 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =7.3 Hz, H-6), 5.33 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =6.9 Hz, H-8), 5.30 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =7.5 Hz, H-9), 5.29 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =6.8 Hz, H-11), 5.23 (1H, m, H-12), 2.77 (2H, t, J =6.5 Hz, H₂-2), 2.38 (2H, m, H₂-7), 2.32 (2H, m, H₂-10), 2.08 (2H, m, H₂-4), 2.04 (2H, m, H₂-13), 1.60 (4H, m, 2×CH₂), 1.29 (6H, m, 3×CH₂), 1.26 (6H, m, 3×CH₂), 1.23 (16H, brs, 8×CH₂), 0.86 (3H, t, J =6.6 Hz, Me-26); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ 180.18 (C-1), 130.26 (C-5), 129.98 (C-6, C-8), 129.25 (C-9), 128.07 (C-11), 127.88 (C-12), 34.05 (CH₂), 31.76 (CH₂), 31.48 (CH₂), 29.70-29.12 (14×CH₂), 25.45 (CH₂), 24.60 (CH₂), 22.68 (CH₂), 14.16 (Me-28); +ve ion FAB MS *m/z* (*rel. int.*): 419 [M+H]⁺ (C₂₈H₅₁O₂) (5.3), 331 (5.3), 305 (11.3), 291 (15.6), 265 (25.3), 251 (14.1), 225 (13.5).

***n*-Octacos-11-trienoic acid (5)**

Elution of the column with chloroform gave a colourless powder of **5**, m.p. 94-95 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 3199, 2927, 2848, 1706, 1638, 1465, 1419, 1298, 1225, 940, 727 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 5.33 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =8.1 Hz, H-11), 5.29 (1H, m, $w_{1/2}$ =7.8 Hz, H-12), 2.38 (2H, t, J =7.2 Hz, H₂-2), 2.35 (2H, m, H₂-10), 2.03 (2H, m, H₂-13), 1.65 (4H, m, 2×CH₂), 1.33 (16H, brs, 8×CH₂), 1.28 (14H, brs, 7×CH₂), 1.25 (12H, brs, 6×CH₂), 0.86 (3H, t, J =6.6 Hz, Me-30); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ 180.61 (C-1), 129.93 (C-11), 129.72 (C-12), 34.16 (CH₂), 31.90 (CH₂), 29.68-29.05 (21×CH₂), 27.21 (CH₂), 24.66 (CH₂), 22.69 (CH₂), 14.15 (Me-28); +ve ion FAB MS *m/z* (*rel. int.*): 423 [M+H]⁺ (C₂₈H₅₅O₂) (23.1), 279 (82.6).

Results and discussion

Compound **1** showed IR absorption bands for ester group (1725 cm⁻¹), unsaturation (1635 cm⁻¹) and long aliphatic chain (722 cm⁻¹). Its mass spectrum exhibited a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 337 (C₂₂H₄₃O₂) [M+H]⁺. The ion peaks arising at *m/z* 279 [CH₃(C₁₆H₂₈)COO]⁺ and 263 [CH₃(C₁₆H₂₈)CO]⁺ indicated that linoleic acid was esterified with *n*-butanol. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **1** displayed four one-proton vinylic protons between δ 5.33-5.22, a two-proton triplet at δ 4.13 (J =6.9 Hz) due to oxygenated methylene H₂-1' protons, other methylene protons from δ 2.75 to 1.25 and two three-proton triplets at δ 0.89 (J =6.5 Hz) and 0.85 (J =6.6 Hz) ascribed to terminal C-18 and C-4' primary methyl protons, respectively. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of **1** had signals for ester carbons at δ 173.69 (C-1), vinylic carbons between δ 131.16-127.83, oxygenated methylene carbon at δ 61.05 (C-1') and methyl carbons at δ 14.18 (C-18) and 14.09 (C-4'). On the basis of these evidences the structure of **1** has been characterised as *n*-butanyl *n*-octadec-9,12-dienoate (Figure 1).

Compound **2**, [M+H]⁺ at *m/z* 463 (C₃₁H₅₉O₂), showed IR absorption bands for ester group (1723 cm⁻¹), unsaturation (1640 cm⁻¹) and long aliphatic chain (723 cm⁻¹). The mass ion peaks arising at *m/z* 279 and 263 similar to compound **1** suggested that linoleic acid was esterified with *n*-tridecanol. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **2** displayed four one-proton multiplets from δ 5.32 to 5.27 assigned to vinylic protons, a two-proton triplet at δ 4.15 (J =7.2 Hz) ascribed to oxygenated methylene H₂-1' protons, other methylene protons between δ 2.75-1.25 and two three-proton triplets at δ 0.86 (J =6.6 Hz) and 0.83 (J =6.5 Hz) accounted to terminal C-18 and C-13' primary methyl protons. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of **2** exhibited signals for ester carbon at δ 173.67 (C-1), vinylic carbons from 130.32-127.91, oxygenated methylene carbon at δ 60.83 (C-1'), other methylene carbons from δ 34.11 to 22.68 and methyl carbons at δ 14.15 (C-18) and 14.09 (C-13'). These data led to identify **2** as *n*-tridecanyl *n*-octadec-9,12-dienoate (Figure 1). Compound **3** was the known fatty acid identified as arachidic acid (Figure 1).

Compound **4** gave effervescences with sodium bicarbonate solution. Its IR spectrum showed absorption bands for carboxylic group (3210, 1709 cm⁻¹), unsaturation (1640 cm⁻¹) and long aliphatic chain (722 cm⁻¹). The mass spectrum of **4** had a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 419 [M+H]⁺ (C₂₈H₅₁O₂) and ion fragments generating at *m/z* 331 [C-4-

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